

Name	Organisation	Role/Position	Category	Level of Engagement	Website
Mayor of Athienou	Athienou Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.athienou.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Athienou	Athienou Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.athienou.org.cy
Mayor of Ayia Napa	Ayia Napa Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.agianapa.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Ayia Napa	Ayia Napa Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.agianapa.org.cy
A.Vionitis	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.gov.cy/moi/
N/A	Ministry of Interior	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.gov.cy/moi/
O. Michaelides	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.gov.cy/moi/
Head of Cyprus Energy Regulatory A	Cyprus Energy Regulatory A	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.cera.org.cy
R. Michaelides	Cyprus Energy Regulatory A	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.cera.org.cy
Agis Piperides	Cyta-Cyprus Telecommunica	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.cyta.com.cy
G. Theopocopoulos	Department of Agriculture, M	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.da.moa.gov.cy
M. Papanicolaou	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.environment.moa.gov.cy
N. Kytheotou	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.environment.moa.gov.cy
A. Chrystou	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.fd.moa.gov.cy
A. Matsikaris	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.dom.moa.gov.cy
K. Nicolaidis	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.dom.moa.gov.cy
M. Kanga	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.dom.moa.gov.cy
A. Georgiadou	Department of Town Plannin	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.tph.moi.gov.cy
N/A	Dept. of Antiquities (MCW)	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.dam.moa.gov.cy
S. Kolios	Dept. of Civil Aviation (MCW)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.dca.mcw.gov.cy
C. Papadopoulos	Dept. of Labour Inspection (I	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.dil.mlsi.gov.cy
M. Orphanides	Dept. of Labour Inspection (I	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.dil.mlsi.gov.cy
Ana Agapothokleous	Dept. of Town Planning & Hc	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.papd.mof.gov.cy
Christos Petrides	Deputy Ministry of Tourism	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.visitcyprus.com
O. Theocharous	Deputy Ministry of Tourism	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.visitcyprus.com
Vakis Loizides	Deputy Ministry of Tourism	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.visitcyprus.com
Gavriela Gavriel	Deryneia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.deryneia.org.cy
S. Isaias	Electrical & Mechanical Serv	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.ems.mcw.gov.cy
C. Pallas	Electricity Authority of Cypru	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.eac.com.cy
S. Papadopoulos	Electricity Authority of Cypru	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.eac.com.cy
N/A	Fire Service	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.fs.gov.cy
Nicos Mardas	Fire Service	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.fs.gov.cy
Director of Cyprus Geological Survey	Geological Survey Dept (MC	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.gsd.moa.gov.cy
G. Hadjigeorgiou	Geological Survey Dept (MC	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.gsd.moa.gov.cy
Mayor of Geroskipou	Geroskipou Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.geroskipou.org.cy
K. Anastasiades	Geroskipou Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.geroskipou.org.cy
Mayor of Kourion	Kourion Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.kourion.org
Valentina Michael	Kourion Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.kourion.org
Mayor of Lakatameia	Lakatameia Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.lakatameia.org.cy
A. Palaigianni	Larnaca Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.larnaca.org.cy
V. Daniel	Larnaca Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.larnaca.org.cy
Andreas Vyras	Larnaca Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.larnaca.org.cy
Andreas Louca	Larnaca Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.larnaca.org.cy
Christos Pittaras	Latsia-Geri Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.latsia-geri.org.cy
Municipal Secretary Αποτίσιμ-επίλο	Latsia-Geri Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.latsia-geri.org.cy
Mayor of Lefkara	Lefkara Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.lefkara.org.cy
C. Chadjiannou	Lefkara Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.lefkara.org.cy
Mayor of Limassol	Limassol Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.limassol.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Limassol	Limassol Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.limassol.org.cy
E. Ioannou	Ministry of Defence	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mod.gov.cy
I. Hadjimichael	Ministry of Defence	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mod.gov.cy
P. Stylianides	Ministry of Defence	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mod.gov.cy
C. Antonides	Ministry of Education	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.mpec.gov.cy
M. Yiallouras	Ministry of Education	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.mpec.gov.cy
C. Ellinopoulos	Ministry of Energy/Commerc	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.meci.gov.cy
N/A	Ministry of Finance	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mof.gov.cy
Ana Panayiotou	Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mfa.gov.cy
P. Samouits	Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mfa.gov.cy
K. Kourou	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.moi.gov.cy
M. Andronicou	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.moi.gov.cy
N. Mannouris	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.moi.gov.cy
S. Meletiou	Ministry of Interior	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.moi.gov.cy
N. Nicolau	Ministry of Labour, Welfare &	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.mls.gov.cy
A. Hadjipakkos	Nicosia District Administratio	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.nicda.moi.gov.cy
G. Mathopoulos	Nicosia District Administratio	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.nicda.moi.gov.cy
I. Ghogaki	Nicosia District Administratio	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.nicda.moi.gov.cy
Afroditi Hajianastasi	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Charalambos Papadopoulos	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Christos Athanasios	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Dimitris Angelidis	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Koula Ioannou	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Menelaos Avraam	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Nicos Pampoulos	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Dinos Logides	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Myria Pliakouta	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosiamunicipality.org.cy
Mayor of Pafos	Pafos Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pafos.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Pafos	Pafos Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pafos.org.cy
Mayor of Paralimni	Paralimni Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.paralimni.org.cy
Mayor of Akama	Pegelia Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pegeiamunicipality.com
Municipal Secretary of Akama	Pegelia Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pegeiamunicipality.com
Police	Police office	Office info contact	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.police.gov.cy
Mayor of Polis Chrysochou	Polis Chrysochou Municipa	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.polis.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Polis Chryso	Polis Chrysochou Municipa	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.polis.org.cy
Marilena Papastavrou	Press & Info Office of the Republic	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.prsinfo.gov.cy
P. Charilaou	Press & Info Office (MOH)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mphs.moh.gov.cy
P. Rodotheou	Press & Info Office (MOH)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.mphs.moh.gov.cy
C. Naoum	Public Works Dept (MCW)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pwdf.mcw.gov.cy
N/A	Public Works Dept (MCW)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pwdf.mcw.gov.cy
G. Protopapa	Public Works Dept (MCW)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.pwdf.mcw.gov.cy
Sewerage Board of Nicosia	Sewerage Board of Nicosia	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.sbn.org.cy
A. Katsouni	-	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.sgl.moi.gov.cy
P. Mouzouras	-	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.sgps.mof.gov.cy
Mayor of South Nicosia	South Nicosia-Idalion Municip	Mayor	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.sni.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of South Nicosia	South Nicosia-Idalion Municip	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.sni.org.cy
Mayor of Strovolos	Strovolos Municipality	Mayor	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.strovolos.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Strovolos	Strovolos Municipality	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.strovolos.org.cy
A. Pieridou	Treasury of the Republic	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.treasury.gov.cy
A. Elthymiou	Treasury of the Republic	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.treasury.gov.cy
A. Marathefi	Veterinary Services (MOA)	Contact person	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.vs.moa.gov.cy
R. Athanasios	Water Board of Nicosia	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.wbn.org.cy
E. Attkouri	Water Development Dept (M	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.wdd.moa.gov.cy
K. Kymani	Water Development Dept (M	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.wdd.moa.gov.cy
Evelina Mechanikou	Youth Board of Cyprus (ONE	Contact person	Public Authorities	Medium	http://www.onek.org.cy
Mayor of Amathounta	Municipality of Amathounta	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.agosathanasios.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Amathounta	Municipality of Amathounta	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.agosathanasios.org.cy
Mayor of Aradippou Apothirrou	Municipality of Aradippou	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.aradippou.org.cy
Municipal Secretary of Aradippou	Municipality of Aradippou	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.aradippou.org.cy
Mayor of Polemidia	Municipality of Polemidia	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
Municipal Secretary of Polemidia	Municipality of Polemidia	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
Municipal Secretary of Dromolaxia	Municipality of Dromolaxia	Municipal Secretary	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.dromolaxia-meneou.com.cy
Mayor of Dromolaxia	Municipality of Dromolaxia	Mayor	Public Authorities	Low	http://www.gmail.com
Chara Georgiadou	Union of Cyprus Municipalitie	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.ucom.org.cy
Vasiliki Vasileiou	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Giorgos Georgiou	Nicosia Municipality	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.nicosia.org.cy
Joanna Constantinou	Department of Environment	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.environment.moa.gov.cy
Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development & Environment – Dept. of Environment	Ministry of Agriculture, Rural	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.moa.gov.cy
Environmental Department	Ministry of Agriculture, Rural	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	https://eia.moa.gov.cy/public/index.html
Department of Meteorology	Department of Meteorology (I	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.moa.gov.cy
Water Development Department	Water Development Departm	Director	Public Authorities	High	http://www.moa.gov.cy
Town Planning & Housing Department	Ministry of Interior	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.moi.gov.cy
Union of Cyprus Municipalities	Union of Cyprus Municipalitie	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.ucom.org.cy
Department of Forests	Department of Forests (MOA)	Office info contact	Public Authorities	High	http://www.moa.gov.cy
Prof. Panos Hadjinicolaou	Climate and Atmosphere Res	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	http://www.cy.ac.cy
Prof. Marina Neophytou	Faculty of Engineering of the I	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	https://www.ucy.ac.cy/fsee
Dr. Petros Mouzourides	Environmental Fluid Mechan	Contact person	Public Authorities	High	https://efml.ucy.ac.cy
P. Dalias	Agricultural Research Institu	Director	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.arl.moa.gov.cy
A. Soteriou	Cyprus Security Research C	Contact person	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.csrcyprus.org.cy
M. Mina	Cyprus Security Research C	Contact person	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.csrcyprus.org.cy
G. Zitis	The Cyprus Institute	Contact person	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.cyi.ac.cy
I. Sofokleous	The Cyprus Institute	Contact person	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.cyi.ac.cy
N/A	University of Cyprus	Contact person	Research & Academic	Low	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Konstantinos Kounnamas	Frederick University	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ncu.org.cy/index.php/en/
Kouis Panayiotis	University of Cyprus	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Kyriakides Theodoros	University of Cyprus	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Giorgos Alexandrou	University of Cyprus	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Marina Neophytou	University of Cyprus	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Petros Mouzourides	University of Cyprus	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
Vassos Vassiliou	CYENS Centre of Excellence	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	CYENS Centre of Excellence
Panayiotis Charalambous	CYENS Centre of Excellence	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	CYENS Centre of Excellence
Styliani Petroudi	CYENS Centre of Excellence	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	CYENS Centre of Excellence
George Kirkos	CYENS Centre of Excellence	Researcher	Research & Academic	Medium	CYENS Centre of Excellence
N/A	University of Cyprus – Civil E	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ucy.ac.cy
N/A	Frederick University – Schoc	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.frederick.ac.cy
N/A	Frederick University - Nature	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ncu.org.cy/index.php/en/
N/A	European University Cyprus	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.euc.ac.cy
N/A	Open University of Cyprus –	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.ouc.ac.cy
N/A	KIOS Research and Innovati	Office info contact	Research & Academic	Medium	http://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy
Michalis Loizides	ISOTECH	Contact person	Research & Academic	Medium	https://teecyprus.org/
Cyprus Agrotourism Company	Cyprus Agrotourism Compar	Office info contact	Business	Low	http://www.agrotourism.com.cy
N/A	CYTANET	Office info contact	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
N/A	CYTANET	Office info contact	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
P. Kostas	CYTANET	Contact person	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
GF. Matheou	CYTANET	Contact person	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
GF. Panayides	CYTANET	Contact person	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy
N/A	CYTANET	Office info contact	Business	Low	http://www.cyanet.com.cy</